

Towards the point of care evaluation/screening of liver grafts using mid-infrared spectroscopy

Table of Contents

Samples and methods.....	1
Load data.....	2
Spectral normalization.....	2
Overview of ATR-FTIR data.....	3
Overview of UPLC-ESI(+/-)-TOFMS lipidomic profiles.....	4
Linear correlation between annotated LC-MS features and the total TAG content.....	4
PCA of lipidomic profiles.....	5
PCA of ATR-FTIR.....	6
Mantel test: IR ~ MS.....	6
Direct quantification of lipid content by ATR-FTIR spectroscopy of dry residues.....	7
Comparing histopathology and FTIR classifications.....	10

***Note: this script requires PLS Toolbox (Eigenvector Research Inc., WA)**

Samples and methods

Samples. A total of 20 liver tissue samples obtained from the Human Liver Collection at the BioBank of the University and Polytechnic Hospital La Fe (Valencia, Spain). This collection comes from donor livers which were primarily assigned to liver transplantation but, due to failings in some of the inclusion criteria (e.g. steatosis) they were donated to research. Liver samples were analyzed and classified according histological information and their TAG contents. The use of these samples for research purposes was approved by the Ethics Committee for Biomedical Research of the Health Research Institute La Fe (Valencia, Spain) with the approval number 2014/0247.

Quantification of TAG in samples. A portion of 15-20 mg frozen liver tissue and 450 μ L water were introduced in a 2 ml polypropylene tube containing CK14 ceramic beads (Precellys, France) for tissue homogenization (2 homogenization cycles of 25 s at 6,000 rpm and 5 ° C) in a Precellys 24 Dual system (Precellys). 400 μ L were collected and mixed with 500 μ L CH₃OH and 1 mL CHCl₃. The sample was homogenized (vortex, 30 s), left on ice for 10 min, and centrifuged at 10,000 x g (15 min, 4°C). The lipid phase (CHCl₃) was collected, centrifuged (10,000 x g, 15 min, 4°C), evaporated to dryness and re-dissolved in 40 μ L isopropanol. Total TAGs content was analyzed with a colorimetric kit (Spinreact, Barcelona, Spain).

Lipidomic analysis. A portion of 20-40 mg frozen tissue was mixed with CH₂Cl:CH₃OH (2:1) (20 μ l/mg tissue) in a 2 ml polypropylene tube containing CK14 ceramic beads (Precellys, France) for tissue homogenization (3 homogenization cycles of 40 s at 6,000 rpm and 5 ° C, with pauses of 30 s between cycles) in a Precellys 24 Dual system (Precellys). Homogenates were collected and transferred to clean microcentrifuge vials for centrifugation (13,000 x g, 10 min, 4 ° C). Then, the supernatant was collected and 4 μ l H₂O/mg tissue were added. The mixture was homogenized (vortex, 20s) and centrifuged (2,000 x g, 5 min, 4C). The organic phase was withdrawn and evaporated to dryness (SpeedVac). The residue was dissolved in 150 μ l (1:1) (5:1:4 IPA:CH₃OH:H₂O, 5 mM CH₃COONH₄, 0.1% v/v HCOOH):(99:1 IPA:H₂O, 5 mM CH₃COONH₄, 0.1% v/v HCOOH). A blank extract was prepared following the same procedure but replacing tissue samples with water.

For quality control, 10 μL of each sample extract were pooled in a glass vial to create a quality control (QC) sample.

Untargeted metabolomic analysis was carried out employing a 1290 Infinity ultra performance liquid chromatograph (UPLC) system from Agilent Technologies (CA, USA) equipped with a UPLC BEH C18 column (50 x 2.1 mm, 1.7 μm) from Waters (Wexford, Ireland). Full scan MS and MS2 data in the range between 50 and 1500 m/z were acquired using an Agilent 6550 Spectrometer iFunnel quadrupole time-of-flight (QTOF) MS system. Samples were analyzed in two independent batches using positive and negative electrospray ionization (ESI+/-).

ATR-FTIR analysis. Infrared spectra in the 3000 to 700 cm^{-1} range were obtained on a ReactIR15 FTIR (Mettler-Toledo, Columbus, USA) spectrometer equipped with a liquid nitrogen-refrigerated mercury–cadmium–telluride detector. No purge system was required. Measurements were made using an AgX probe (9.5 mm x 1 m) accessory equipped with a diamond sensor composite (DiComp™) and a ZnSe focusing element for ATR, with a recommended working optical range from 2800 to 650 cm^{-1} . A portion of ~5-10 mg of liver sample was deposited in the center of the ATR crystal and left for 15 s. Then, the sample was removed and 20 s after its removal, a spectrum of the dry residue was collected co-adding 256 scans with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . A spectrum of air previously recorded using the same instrumental conditions was used as background. The total measurement time including background acquisition was less than 4 minutes. After each measurement, the ATR surface was cleaned using a cotton swab and H₂O, isopropanol, CH₃OH and H₂O consecutively until recovery of the baseline signal. Spectral acquisition order was randomized to avoid biased results due to instrumental effects, but sample replicates were measured in a row to avoid additional tissue freeze and thaw cycles.

Load data

```
clear
load Liver_IRMS.mat IRs_raw IRt_raw MSs lipids wn
```

IRs_raw (20 x 538): spectra collected from dry residues of the set of 20 liver samples in the 1800-800 cm^{-1} range

IRt_raw (20 x 538): spectra directly collected from the set of 20 liver samples in the 1800-800 cm^{-1} range

MSs (20 x 536): lipidomic data from the analysis of the analysis of the set of 20 liver samples

lipids (20 x 1): total TAGs ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ protein)

wn (1 x 538): wavenumbers (1800-800 cm^{-1} range)

Spectral normalization

ATR-FTIR spectra were normalized using standard normal variate (SNV) normalization (i.e. using the standard deviation of all the pooled variables of each spectrum as normalization factor).

```
IRt_raw_snv = preprocess('calibrate',preprocess('default','snv'),IRt_raw);
IRs_raw_snv = preprocess('calibrate',preprocess('default','snv'),IRs_raw);
```

Overview of ATR-FTIR data

The following figure shows the ATR-FTIR spectrum of four thaw liver tissues (#1, 3, 6, and 12) with different TAG concentrations in the 1800-800 cm^{-1} range. Spectra were acquired after positioning each liver sample on top of the ATR surface (Figure 1 left-top), and after removing the sample and waiting 20 s for the generation of the dry residue (Figure 1 right-top). The Figure also shows the spectra after SNV(see Figure 1, bottom).

The main spectral contributions were derived from proteins, carbohydrates, phosphate bands from phospholipids, DNA and RNA, and lipids. Minor band shifts were observed between the spectra of hydrated and dry samples. The intense and broad bands of water in the spectra of hydrated samples strongly overlaps with tissue-derived bands in the 1600-1700 cm^{-1} region, reducing the signal to noise ratio, and the repeatability of the measurements.

The bands at 1650 cm^{-1} (protein amide I), 1547 cm^{-1} (protein amide II), and 1309 cm^{-1} (protein amide III) [21] could be discerned in the absorbance spectrum of dry residues. Characteristic bands associated to lipids at 1749 cm^{-1} (saturated ester C=O stretch from lipids and cholesterol esters), 1456 cm^{-1} (CH₂ bending of lipidic acyl chains), 1402 cm^{-1} (COO⁻ symmetric stretch of fatty acids and amino acids) were also present in the spectrum. Furthermore, the 1300-900 cm^{-1} region contains several overlapped bands from C-O and P-O stretching modes from lipids, phospholipids, carbohydrates and nucleic acids. Bands at 1240 cm^{-1} (PO₂-antisymmetric stretch from phospholipids[22] and nucleic acids[23]) and 1081 cm^{-1} (PO₂- symmetric stretch from phospholipids and nucleic acids) could be appreciated, as well as glycogen bands[24,25] at 1156 cm^{-1} (CO-O-C antisymmetric stretching of glycogen and nucleic acids) and 1027 cm^{-1} (C-O stretching of glycogen). The glycogen band at 1040 cm^{-1} seems to overlap with the PO₂- band at 1081 cm^{-1} .

```
figure ('name', 'Figure 1. ATR-FTIR spectra', 'Position', [150 200 1250 650])
subplot(2,2,1)
plot(wn, IRT_raw.data([1 3 6 12], :), 'LineWidth', 2)
title('Liver tissue', 'FontWeight', 'bold')

subplot(2,2,2)
plot(wn, IRs_raw.data([1 3 6 12], :), 'LineWidth', 2)
title('Dry residue', 'FontWeight', 'bold')

subplot(2,2,3)
plot(wn, IRT_raw_snv.data([1 3 6 12], :), 'LineWidth', 2)
title('Liver tissue (SNV)', 'FontWeight', 'bold')
ylim([-2 4])

subplot(2,2,4)
plot(wn, IRs_raw_snv.data([1 3 6 12], :), 'LineWidth', 2)
title('Dry residue (SNV)', 'FontWeight', 'bold')
ylim([-2 4])

wns = [1749 1650 1547 1456 1402 1240 1156 1081 1027]; % ref wavenumbers
for i = 1:length(wns)
    [ ~, ix ] = min( abs( wn-wns(i) ) );
    subplot(2,2,1)
    h = text(wns(i), IRT_raw.data(3, ix), num2str(wns(i)), 'FontSize', 15);
    set(h, 'Rotation', 90)
    subplot(2,2,2)
    h = text(wns(i), IRs_raw.data(3, ix), num2str(wns(i)), 'FontSize', 15);
```

```

set(h, 'Rotation', 90)
subplot(2,2,3)
h = text(wns(i), IRT_raw_snv.data(3,ix), num2str(wns(i)), 'FontSize', 15);
set(h, 'Rotation', 90)
subplot(2,2,4)
h = text(wns(i), IRs_raw_snv.data(3,ix), num2str(wns(i)), 'FontSize', 15);
set(h, 'Rotation', 90)
end
for i = 1:4
    subplot(2,2,i)
xlabel('Wavenumber (cm-1)')
ylabel('Absorbance')
set(gca, 'XDir', 'Reverse', 'FontSize', 16, 'XTick', [800:200:1800])
grid on
xlim([800 1800])
end
clear
load Liver_IRMS.mat % restore workspace

```

Overview of UPLC-ESI(+/-)-TOFMS lipidomic profiles

The comprehensive analysis of the hepatic lipidome is challenging. Nonetheless, the employed strategy for the lipidomic analysis of liver extracts by UPLC-ESI(+/-)-TOFMS enabled the annotation of the major lipid classes (e.g. glycerophospholipids, glycerolipids, fatty acyls or sphingolipids) and subclasses (e.g. TAG, glycerophosphoethanolamines, glycerophosphocholines, glycerophosphoglycerols, or ceramides) constituents of liver (see the following figures and tables).

Plots the distribution of features ~ lipid class

```
plot_idclasses3dso(MSs,0,1) % Plots the distribution of features ~ lipid class
```

Plots the distribution of features ~ lipid subclass

```
plot_idclasses3dso(MSs,0,2) % Plots the distribution of features ~ lipid subclass
```

Plots the distribution of features ~ lipid ESI polarity (positive/negative)

```
plot_idclasses3dso(MSs,0,3) % Plots the distribution of features ~ ESI polarity
```

Linear correlation between annotated LC-MS features and the total TAG content

Each of the 538 annotated features was linearly correlated to the hepatic TAG concentration in the sample set, as estimated by a colorimetric method to get an overview about which changes in the lipidome were associated with the grade of steatosis. Based on the ratio of annotated features with a statistically significant (p -value <0.05) linear association to the TAG content, four subclasses (glycerophosphoethanolamines, glycerophosphocholines, glycerophosphoinositols, and glycerophosphoserines) could be identified that were inversely correlated. On the other hand, triacylglycerols, diacylglycerols, fatty alcohols and linoleic acids

and derivatives were mostly positively correlated to the TAG concentrations enzymatically measured (see the following table).

```
J = size(MSs,2);
for j = 1:J
    model_ = fitlm(lipids,log(MSs.data(:,j)));
    b(j,1) = model_.Coefficients.Estimate(2);
    b_pval(j,1) = model_.Coefficients.pValue(2);
end
t1 = MSs.classid{2,2}'; % lipid subclasses
for i = 1:size(t1,1)
    t2(i,1) = string(t1(i,1));
end
unique_class = unique(t2,'rows');
for i = 1:size(unique_class,1)
    [temp_class, ~] = find(strcmp(t2,unique_class(i))>0);
    n_unique_class(i,1) = numel(temp_class);
    n_sign_lipids(i,1) = numel(find(b_pval(temp_class)<0.05));
    n_sign_lipids_up(i,1) = numel(find(b_pval(temp_class)<0.05 & b(temp_class)>0));
    n_sign_lipids_down(i,1) = numel(find(b_pval(temp_class)<0.05 & b(temp_class)<0));
end
% output table
MSs_correlations = table(unique_class,n_unique_class,n_sign_lipids_up,n_sign_lipids_down);
[MSs_correlations, ~] = sortrows(MSs_correlations,2,'descend');
```

PCA of lipidomic profiles

The first two principal components (PCs) accounted for 16.4% and 14.4%, of the total variation in the autoscaled lipidomic dataset, respectively. PC1 was associated to the relative TAGs content, indicating that this was one of the main sources of variation.

```
clear
load Liver_IRMS.mat % restore workspace

options_pca = pca('options');
options_pca.display = 'off';
options_pca.plots = 'final';
options_pca.preprocessing = {preprocess('default', 'autoscale')};
model_pca_IR = pca(MSs,5,options_pca);
% use the plot controls to customize the view (e.g. PC1-PC2, labels
% features ~ class or subclass, label samples~patient number, color
% samples~TAG contents in MSs.axisscale{2,1}, ...)
% plotscore(model_pca)
```

PC1 was associated to the relative TAGs content, indicating that this was one of the main sources of variation (see Figure 3A). Figure 3B shows the loadings plot with metabolites labelled according to their class for better visualization (a detailed version of the same plot displaying the subclasses can be found in the Supplementary Material Figure S1). The loadings plot indicated that glycerolipid (mainly TAGs and DAGs) and glycerophospholipid concentrations were inversely correlated, and that the ratio glycerolipids/glycerophospholipids was highly associated to the first PC. Distribution of samples along PC2 was partially

linked to their relative concentrations of sphingolipids, steroid and steroid derivatives and a group of glycerophospholipids with low loadings in PC2.

PCA of ATR-FTIR

The first two principal components (PCs) accounted for 79.4% and 12.4%, of the total variation in the dataset, respectively. PC1 was associated to the relative TAGs content, indicating that this was one of the main sources of variation.

```
SD = preprocess('default','derivative'); % calculate the second derivative
SD.userdata.deriv = 2;
SD.userdata.width = 15;
IR2s_snv = preprocess('calibrate',SD,IRs_raw_snv);

options_pca = pca('options');
options_pca.display = 'off';
options_pca.plots = 'final';
options_pca.preprocessing = {preprocess('default', 'mean center')};

model_pca_MS = pca(IR2s_snv,5,options_pca);
% use the plot controls to customize the view (e.g. PC1-PC2, labels
% features ~ class or subclass, label samples~patient number, color
% samples~TAG contents in MSs.axisscale{2,1}, ...)
% plotscore(model_pca)
```

The first PC was again associated to the relative TAG contents, leading to a remarkable separation of livers according to their total TAGs content. Loadings for the first and second PC depicted in Figure 3D showed that spectral regions associated to lipid and phospholipids centered around 1749 and 1456 cm^{-1} presented higher loading values in the first PC. Considering the PCA was performed over the second derivative of the spectra, this implies that negative PC1 score values should be correlated with higher absorbance in these regions and hence with larger TAG content.

Mantel test: IR ~ MS

The Mantel test [*N. Mantel, The detection of disease clustering and a generalized regression approach, Cancer Res. 27 (1967) 209–220*] was then applied to evaluate the correlation between the PCA scores plots obtained using ATR-FTIR and UPLC-TOFMS data. This test evaluates the significance of the correlation between pairwise distance matrices. In this study, the standardized Euclidean multivariate distances between matched sample pairs were used. The statistical significance of the Mantel test distance (r) was determined by a permutation test (10000 permutations).

```
clear
load Liver_IRMS.mat % restore workspace

SD = preprocess('default','derivative'); % calculate the second derivative
SD.userdata.deriv = 2;
SD.userdata.width = 15;
IR2s_snv = preprocess('calibrate',SD,IRs_raw_snv); X1 = IR2s_snv.data;
n = size(X1,1);
```

```

mX1 = mean(X1);
stdX1 = std(X1);
X1 = (X1-mX1(ones(n,1),:)); % mean center, second derivative-SNV IR data

X2 = MSs.data;
mX2 = mean(X2);
stdX2 = std(X2);
X2 = (X2-mX2(ones(n,1),:))./stdX2(ones(n,1),:); % autoscale MS data

% PCA (2 PCs)
[U_IR,D_IR,V_IR] = svd(X1,'econ');
IR_scores = X1*V_IR(:,1:2);
[U_MS,D_MS,V_MS] = svd(X2,'econ');
MS_scores = X2*V_MS(:,1:2);

d1_scores = pdist(MS_scores,'euclidean');
d2_scores = pdist(IR_scores,'euclidean');
temp = corrcoef(d1_scores,d2_scores);
    mantel_d1_d2_scores = temp(1,2);
% Permutation test
for i=1:10000
    IP = randperm(numel(d1_scores));
    d1_scoresP = d1_scores(IP);
    temp = corrcoef(d1_scoresP,d2_scores);
    mantel_d1_d2_scoresP(i) = temp(1,2);
end
figure('name','Mantel test. Distancia Euclidea - Scores space')
histogram(mantel_d1_d2_scoresP,100)
hold on
plot(mantel_d1_d2_scores,0,'ko','MarkerFaceColor','r','MarkerSize',12)
xlabel('Mantet test (IR-MS, PCA scores space)','FontSize',14)
ylabel('Frequency','FontSize',14)
set(gca,'FontSize',16)
p_mantel_d1_d2_scores = (1+numel(find(abs(mantel_d1_d2_scoresP)>=mantel_d1_d2_scores)))
if p_mantel_d1_d2_scores<0.001
title('All samples: p-value Mantel test <0.001','FontWeight','bold')
else
title(['p-value Mantel test: ',num2str(round(p_mantel_d1_d2_scores,3))],'FontWeight','b')
end
end

```

Direct quantification of lipid content by ATR-FTIR spectroscopy of dry residues

A multivariate PLS regression method was developed for the quantification of the relative concentration of TAGs, using the 1800-800 cm⁻¹ spectral region and standard normal variate and autoscale as spectral preprocessing. Statistical validation was carried out by leave one out - cross validation (CV) and, to avoid over optimistic results, no variable selection step was included during model development.

```

X = IRs_raw_snv;
y = lipids;

options_pls = pls('options');
options_pls.display = 'off';
options_pls.plots = 'none';

```

```

options_pls.preprocessing = {preprocess('autoscale') preprocess('autoscale')};
max_lvs = 5;

% pls CV parameteres
options_cv = crossval('options');
options_cv.display = 'off';
options_cv.plots = 'none';
options_cv.preprocessing = options_pls.preprocessing;

% pls model calc.
modell_train = pls(X,y,max_lvs,options_pls);
% VIP scores vector (model #1)
vip_modell = vip(modell_train);
% CV
results = crossval(X,y,'nip',{'loo'},max_lvs,options_pls);
[min_rmsecv, lvs] = min(results.rmsecv)

```

The following figure shows the CV-predicted lipid concentrations using 2 latent variables providing a RMSECV = 316 µg/mg protein.

```

figure('name','PLS yhat CV','position',[50 100 400 400])
ycv = results.cvpred(:, :, lvs);
plot(lipids, ycv, 'ko', 'MarkerFaceColor', [0.93 0.69 0.13], 'MarkerSize', 10)
hold on
h = lsline;
h.Color = [0.47 0.67 0.19];
h.LineWidth = 2;
h = refline(1,0); % adds a reference line with slope m and intercept b to the current a
h.Color = 'r';
h.LineWidth = 2;
xlabel('Reference TAGs (\mug/mg prot.)', 'FontSize', 14)
ylabel('PLS CV-predicted TAGs (\mug/mg prot.)', 'FontSize', 14)
xlim([0 max([lipids; ycv])])
ylim([0 max([lipids; ycv])])
legend({'cv-yhat', 'Fit', '1:1'}, 'location', 'northwest')
set(gca, 'FontSize', 14)
grid on
box on

```

The statistical significance of the model was assessed by permutation testing (250 permutations), providing a p-value < 0.005, thus indicating that the model was significant at the 95% confidence level.

```

% permutation test
rng('default') % Set the random number generator to the default seed (0) and algorithm
true.r = 1;
true.lvs = lvs;
true.rmsecv = results.rmsecv(lvs);
true.rmsec = results.rmsec(lvs);
true.r2cv = results.r2cv(lvs);
permutations = 250;
for i = 1:permutations
    P = randperm(numel(y));
    yP = y(P);

```

```

r = corrcoef(y,yP);
perm.r(i) = r(1,2);
modell_trainP = pls(X,yP,max_lvs,options_pls);
resultsP = crossval(X,yP,'nlp',{'loo'},max_lvs,options_pls);
[~, lvsP] = min(resultsP.rmsecv);
perm.lvsP(i) = lvsP;
perm.rmsecv(i) = resultsP.rmsecv(lvsP);
perm.rmsec(i) = resultsP.rmsec(lvsP);
perm.r2cv(i) = resultsP.r2cv(lvsP);
end
p_value_rmsec = (1+sum(perm.rmsec<true.rmsec))/permutations;
p_value_rmsecv = (1+sum(perm.rmsecv<true.rmsecv))/permutations;

figure ('name','Results from permutation test','position',[50 100 400 400])
plot([true.r, abs(perm.r)], [true.rmsec, perm.rmsec],'k^','MarkerFaceColor',[0.93 0.69])
hold on
h = lsline;
h.Color = [0.85 0.33 0.1];
h.LineWidth = 2;
plot([true.r, abs(perm.r)], [true.rmsecv, perm.rmsecv],'ko','MarkerFaceColor',[0.3 0.75])
hold on
lsline
xlabel('Correlation permuted y to original y','FontSize',14)
ylabel('RMSEC and RMSECV','FontSize',14)
xlim([0 1])
legend({'RMSEC','Fit RMSEC','RMSECV','Fit RMSECV'],'location','northeast')
set(gca,'FontSize',14)
grid on
box on

```

The analysis of the importance of the different infrared variables and their contribution to the model was carried out considering the Variable Importance in Projection (VIP) and the regression vector, respectively. Figure 6D shows the average spectra of the liver with a color scale corresponding to the value of each wavenumber in the regression vector. On the other hand, the VIP scores summarized the importance for the predictions of each feature and, since the mean value of the squared VIP scores is one, the VIP>1 rule is widely used as a feature selection criterion. As expected, bands centered at 1749, 1456, and 1402 cm⁻¹ associated to lipids show high positive values of the regression vector, and VIP values greater than 1.

```

figure ('name','Figure VIPs @PLS(dry residues)','position',[50 100 1300 400])
plot(wn,IRs_raw_snv.data(16,:),'k.--')
hold on
scatter(wn,IRs_raw_snv.data(16,:),30,vip_modell,'filled')
xlabel('Wavenumber (cm-1)','FontSize',14)
ylabel('Normalized and scaled absorbance','FontSize',14)
set(gca,'FontSize',14,'XTick',[600:200:3000],'XDir','Reverse','FontSize',14)
grid on
xlim([min(wn) max(wn)])
box off
plot (1720:1770,0,'sr','MarkerFaceColor','r','MarkerSize',10)
text(1795,0.25,'1770-1720 cm-1','FontSize',14)
colorbar

```

Comparing histopathology and FTIR classifications

Liver samples were clustered according to the relative TAG content as: low (<200 ug/mg), low-middle (200-550 ug/mg), middle-high (500-1250 ug/mg), and high (>1250 ug/mg).

This new sub-classification is included to the IR dataset.

```
low_conc = find(lipids<202);
lowmid_conc = find(lipids>=202 & lipids<560);
midhigh_conc = find(lipids>=560 & lipids<1250);
high_conc = find(lipids>=1250);
IRs_raw_snv.classname{1,3} = 'Lipid Conc.';
IRs_raw_snv.class{1,3}(low_conc) = 1;
IRs_raw_snv.class{1,3}(lowmid_conc) = 2;
IRs_raw_snv.class{1,3}(midhigh_conc) = 3;
IRs_raw_snv.class{1,3}(high_conc) = 4;
```

Now, using the CV-PLS predicted y values for TAGs, build a table describing the PLS predicted content according to this classification.

```
yhat_cv = results.cvpred(:, :, 2);
for i = 1:4
ct(i,1) = sum(IRs_raw_snv.class{1,3}==i);
ct(i,2) = sum(yhat_cv(find(IRs_raw_snv.class{1,3}==i))<202);
ct(i,3) = sum(yhat_cv(find(IRs_raw_snv.class{1,3}==i))>=202 & yhat_cv(find(IRs_raw_snv.
ct(i,4) = sum(yhat_cv(find(IRs_raw_snv.class{1,3}==i))>=560 & yhat_cv(find(IRs_raw_snv.
ct(i,5) = sum(yhat_cv(find(IRs_raw_snv.class{1,3}==i))>=1250);
end
ct = array2table(ct, 'VariableNames', {'N', 'pred. as low', 'pred as low-mid', 'pred as mid-
'RowNames', {'low', 'low-mid', 'mid-high', 'high'}})
```

Results summarized in the prev. table show that, as expected, information extracted from the IR spectrum can be used for the stratification of livr steatosis.